

The impact of religious and cultural values on the development of student integrity: gender as a moderating variable

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ABSTRACT

The problem and aim of the study. The primary issue addressed was the apparent gap in understanding the differential impact of these values on student integrity, particularly in diverse and multicultural settings. The aim was to explore the extent to which these values shaped students' ethical and moral development and to determine if gender influenced this relationship.

Research methods. This research employed a quantitative methodology grounded in an explanatory model. The study involved 370 participants from 26 randomly selected high schools in South Sumatra. Data was gathered using a closed-ended Likert scale and analyzed using the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach, a method suitable for assessing complex relationships between variables. The study focused on three key variables: religious values, cultural values, and student integrity, with gender as the moderating variable.

Results. The quantitative results of the study indicated that cultural values significantly positively impact student integrity, with a t-value of 4.390 and a P-value of 0.000. However, religious values did not show a significant positive effect on student integrity with a t-value of 1.826 and P-value of 0.069. In contrast, gender did moderate the relationship between cultural values and student integrity, indicating that both male and female students internalize and express cultural values differently, thereby enhancing student integrity.

Conclusion. The study concluded that cultural values significantly shaped student integrity, whereas religious values did not have a similar effect. Gender moderated the relationship between cultural values and student integrity but did not influence the relationship between religious values and integrity. This highlighted the need for educational strategies that emphasized cultural values and considered gender differences to promote integrity among students effectively. Future research was recommended to expand to different cultural and religious contexts to validate these findings and further explore the complex dynamics between these variables.

KEYWORDS

cultural values, gender, religious values, student integrity

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INTRODUCTION

International educational initiatives spearheaded by organizations such as UNESCO, the Council of Europe, and the International Association of Universities (IAU) play a pivotal role in shaping global educational policies and practices. For instance, UNESCO's «Futures of Education Initiative» focuses on envisioning a more inclusive and sustainable future for education, highlighting the significance of education for sustainable development [1]. Additionally, UNESCO, in collaboration with the Council of Europe and the IAU, has developed various policies and programs to promote lifelong learning, vocational education, and the enhancement of teacher quality [2]. These initiatives aim to create educational systems capable of addressing current and future global needs, ensuring equitable access, and improving the quality of education worldwide.

Formal education, including schools, stands as the primary institution where students systematically and purposefully encounter educational experiences. Education serves as the main gateway for the transfer of knowledge, cultural behaviors, and language to students [3]. According to the Ministry of National Education (2010), schools are crucial in placing women and men equally and fairly in various functional positions and roles. Additionally, posits that school culture should encompass all aspects of the physical environment, atmosphere, characteristics, and school climate, effectively contributing to positive experiences for the growth and development of students' intelligence, skills, and activities [6; 7]. Cultivating values among students involves faith and piety, community, respect for others, awareness of responsibility, safety, cleanliness, orderliness, aesthetics, and the relationships between students and the entire school community [8]. A school is considered moderate if it can create a comfortable, moderate, and evolving environment, thereby fostering an intelligent generation [9]. Furthermore, schools should implement moderate religious practice, which includes tolerance, anti-crime commitment, national commitment, and accommodation of local culture [10]. In this regard, the role of schools is pivotal and can significantly impact student integrity, thereby enhancing intelligence and comprehensive understanding. Furthermore, K.A. Tasoulis et al. [11] discusses integrity as a form of action commitment involving principles and morally justified values. A person of high integrity is affiliated with positive behavior, and moral vision, and is precise in thinking and acting. In the academic field, integrity tends toward a tendency of individuals to act and behave by norms of truthfulness and uphold effective idealism in the academic context. Bretag [12] states that academic integrity is a primary part of academic culture, referring to morals, honesty, and self-unity; in terms of moral character, academic integrity deals not only with violations but also with doing the right thing and taking pride in meeting the highest moral standards in academic activities. With the creation of an academic integrity culture in the school environment, academic integrity morals will be formed among students. Academic integrity issues include not only dishonesty and plagiarism in academics but also committed behavior in honesty, responsibility, trust, fairness, and respect for the work of others [13].

Students who possess good academic integrity will produce consistent behavioral patterns, leading their activities to align with values of goodness. The strength of integrity is developed through habitual processes and the instillation of values in character, behavior, and attitudes, grounded in social norms and religious principles [14]. In the academic environment, students need to be reinforced in integrity by looking through honesty, responsibility, tolerance, and a patriotic attitude [15]. Fundamentally, developing integrity within the educational environment is challenging due to various issues that academic stakeholders face. This is because of the numerous cases that have emerged in the academic environment, such as cheating behavior, impoliteness, students rebelling against their teachers, free association, drug use among students, and others [16]. In addition, many schools lack attention to the development of student behavior related to academic honesty, cheating during exams, consistency with what is said, responsibility towards tasks, and building a relationship with God [17].

Academic integrity can be influenced by various factors, both from within the individual and externally. External factors may include cultural values, while internal factors can be seen from religious values. Religious values concern divinity, belief, and attitudes toward good and bad deeds. Religious values as a manifestation of behavior and attitudes of obedience in practicing religion, tolerance among religions, and living harmoniously. Saroglou et al. [18] describe that religious and cultural values act as social bonds that shape the character of integrity. Trudeau et al. [19] delves into the influence of campus traditions on student life in the campus environment, highlighting the pattern that cultural values influence the character of integrity.

Fundamentally, integrity necessitates that students consistently engage with their surrounding environment, uphold moral standards, remain loyal to existing rules, adhere to their principles, and avoid disrespect or even violations of established laws, as articulated by [20]. Consequently, when a student lacks integrity, there is a significant likelihood of errors occurring in the learning process. An individual's character also influences their behavior and actions. Just as with student integrity, there are differences between male and female students; male students tend to have lower integrity compared to female students. This is attributed to male students typically being more logic-oriented, while female students are more oriented towards emotions. In various cases, male students are more likely to individually engage in academic dishonesty, whereas female students tend to act in groups or follow their peers.

Unfortunately, due to the limited research conducted, especially in Indonesia, the researcher did not find specific references that directly explain the impact of religious and cultural values on the development of student integrity with gender as a moderating variable. Moreover, research in this field may require a multidisciplinary approach that has not been extensively explored, combining insights from psychology, sociology, religious studies, and gender studies. This indicates a gap in the literature that explicitly explores this relationship. The researcher concludes that this study is unique in considering gender as a moderating variable in the relationship between religious values, culture, and student integrity. This allows the research to explore how experiences of integrity may differ between male and female students in various religious and cultural contexts. Based on the aforementioned above, the current research aims to investigate 'the impact of religious values, and cultural values in shaping student integrity with gender as a moderating variable.

The Rationale of the Study

The study entitled *The Impact of Religious and Cultural Values on the Development of Student Integrity: Gender as a Moderating Variable* aims to explore the significant role of religious and cultural values in shaping the ethical and moral compass of students, with a focus on how these influences vary between genders. Understanding that honesty is a crucial quality for academic and personal growth, this study aims to fill a vacuum in the literature by investigating the nuanced ways these values contribute to integrity, particularly in diverse and multicultural contexts. The inclusion of gender as a moderating variable acknowledges potential differences in the development of integrity among male and female students, offering insights for more tailored educational approaches. This study is relevant for educators and policymakers, aiming to contribute to both theoretical understanding and practical applications in fostering ethical behavior in educational settings.

The Study Objectives

The objectives include understanding the influence of religious and cultural values in forming student integrity. Secondly, to ascertain whether gender affects the relationship between spiritual values, cultural values, and the formation of student integrity

The Study of Hypotheses

This study formulated the following hypotheses:

1. H1: Religious value has a positive effect on student integrity.
2. H2: Cultural value has a positive effect on student integrity.
3. H3: Gender has a positive effect on religious values and student integrity.
4. H4: Gender has a positive effect on cultural values and student integrity

RESEARCH METHODS

The Research Design

This study employs a quantitative approach based on the explanatory model. Wong et al. [21] asserts that quantitative research is founded on positivist ideology and utilizes quantitative instruments to gather data from a specific population or sample to assess hypotheses. Explanatory research endeavors to elucidate the relationships between variables and their mutual influences. This

research aims to ascertain the nature and depth of the relationship among three variables: religious values, cultural values, and the integrity of High School Students, mediated by gender.

The Study Sample

The research was conducted in High Schools during the 2020/2021 academic year, specifically targeting 10th-grade classes. There is a total of 110 High Schools. According to Turner [22], when the subject number in a population is exceedingly large, the sample size that can be selected ranges from 10-15% to 20-25%. Therefore, the sample size for this study was determined to be 25% of the population. A random sample of 26 schools was selected from 105 schools. From this number of schools, a proportionally distributed random sampling was used to determine the number of research subjects. The formulation resulted in a total sample size of 370 students from High Schools.

Instrument and Procedure

The data collection technique involved the use of scales. Scales consist of a series of written questions presented to respondents for their responses. The questions are structured based on the research topic or variables involved in the study. The type of scale used in this study is closed-ended. This scale was targeted at 10th-grade students in High Schools in South Sumatra. A Likert scale was used for evaluation. The Likert scale is a tool for assessing opinions, attitudes, and perceptions of an individual or group towards social events or occurrences [21]. The Likert scale level used for measurement ranged from 1-5 (strongly disagree to strongly agree).

The Analysis Data

Data analysis in this research utilized the Partial Least Square (PLS) method. PLS is a variance-based model, functioning under the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) framework. According to Sarstedt et al. [23], describe PLS as a divergent approach that transitions from a covariance-based SEM to a variance-focused SEM. While covariance-based SEM primarily assesses causality and theoretical constructs, PLS leans more toward predictive modeling. One of the strengths of PLS is its minimal reliance on the assumptions of normal distribution and its flexibility in handling smaller sample sizes.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Results

The objectives include understanding the influence of religious and cultural values in forming student integrity. Secondly, to ascertain whether gender affects the relationship between spiritual values, cultural values, and the formation of student integrity. It consisted of two models (1) evaluation of the outer model, and (2) evaluation of the inner model as follows:

Evaluation of the Outer Model

Testing of the outer model is conducted as an initial step before proceeding to hypothesis testing in the inner model. Essentially, the evaluation of the outer model aims to perform early detection of the capability of each indicator in terms of influencing each latent variable present in the research.

The analysis of the outer model using SmartPLS 3 includes evaluating convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. These analytical processes are integral to ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the model developed in the study.

Convergent validity pertains to the principle that manifest variables within a construct exhibit a high correlation. To test for convergent validity, one can examine the loading factor values of each indicator within a construct.

Figure 1 Structural Outer Model

Table 1

Loading Factor Score

	Students Integrity	Cultural Values	Religious Values
In1	0.666		
In10	0.730		
In2	0.808		
In3	0.797		
In4	0.800		
In5	0.684		
In6	0.709		
In7	0.724		
In8	0.791		
In9	0.788		
NB1		0.812	
NB2		0.866	
NB3		0.898	
NB4		0.880	
NB5		0.719	
NB6		0.665	

NK1			0.803
NK2			0.738
NK3			0.849
NK4			0.920
NK5			0.856

Based on the outer loading values from the table above, it can be concluded that the indicators in this study are valid and can be used for further testing, as they meet the specified criterion where the outer loading > 0.6 [23].

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is assessed by contrasting the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct against the correlations among constructs within the model. Discriminant validity is deemed to be strong if the square root of the AVE for each construct exceeds the correlation values between the constructs in the model.

Table 2

AVE Values and Square Root of AVE

	AVE	AVE Root
Gender	1.000	1.000
Gender	0.564	0.751
Students' Integrity	0.658	0.811
Cultural Values	0.698	0.835
Religious Values		

Observing the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values in the table above, all variables have values > 0.50, indicating that each measured indicator validly reflects its respective variable.

Composite Reliability

Composite Reliability is employed to evaluate the reliability of indicators in measuring their latent variables. The criteria for reliability are met if the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values are > 0.7 [23].

Table 3

Composite Reliability dan Cronchbach's Alpha Values

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Gender	1.000	1.000
Students' Integrity	0.914	0.928
Cultural Values	0.900	0.920
Religious Values	0.893	0.920

Evaluation of the Inner Model

The evaluation of the inner model is designed to demonstrate the significance level in hypothesis testing. The calculated figures are compared against established criteria to test the hypotheses derived from the formed constructs. Hypothesis testing is based on results obtained through the

Smart-PLS 3 software, which utilizes bootstrapping for data processing, yielding output in the form of path coefficients and p-values. These two components are subsequently compared against specific criteria to determine whether a hypothesis is supported or not in this research.

Figure 2 Structural Inner Model

Hypothesis testing is evaluated based on the T-statistic and p-value. The purpose of the T-statistic test is to determine the influence between variables within a construct. The T-value used in this research is 1.96 with a significance level of 0.005. If the T-statistic value is greater than 1.96 and the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, then the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4

Path Coefficient Values

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Gender -> Students' Integrity	0.021	0.399	0.690	Rejected
Moderating Effect 1 -> Students' Integrity	0.184	4.063	0.000	Accepted
Moderating Effect 2 -> Students' Integrity	0.035	0.534	0.594	Rejected
Cultural Values -> Students' Integrity	0.216	4.390	0.000	Accepted
Religious values -> Students' Integrity	0.119	1.826	0.069	Rejected

Referring to the table provided, the path coefficient values for the research hypotheses are summarized as follows:

H1: Religious values affects student integrity

From the data processing for high school students, it was found that the t-value is 1.826 with a P-value of 0.069. These results indicate that the t-value is below 1.96 (1.826 < 1.96) and the P-value is above 0.05 (0.069 > 0.05). This suggests that religious values do not significantly influence the

integrity of high school students in South Sumatra. Religious values are manifestations of attitudes and behaviors that adhere to the teachings of one's faith.

H2: Cultural values affect student integrity

Based on the data processing for high school students, it was found that the t-value is 4.390 with a P-value of 0.000. These results indicate that the t-value is above 1.96 ($4.390 > 1.96$) and the P-value is below 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This suggests that cultural values significantly influence the integrity of high school students in South Sumatra. Cultural values within the school environment, such as discipline and punctuality, are influential. In the community, cultural values are highly influential and serve as guidelines or references, such as mutual tolerance, respect, harmony, and cooperation.

H3: Gender affects the relationship between religious values and student integrity

Gender, as an individual characteristic, influences behavior, attitudes, and actions. Females tend to use emotions more in actions, behavior, and attitudes, unlike males who are more inclined to use logic, thus appearing more unemotional. In the research findings, gender does not have an impact on the relationship between religious values and student integrity levels. Religious values are inherently taught from an early age, so their impact on integrity is not significantly large

H4: Gender affects the relationship between cultural values and student integrity

The analysis reveals that gender plays a role in influencing the relationship between cultural values and student integrity. This means that both male and female students impact cultural values, thereby enhancing student integrity.

DISCUSSION

Firstly, *Religious values influence student integrity*. Some academic research gave a positive finding of this – first, a quantitative study by Bekomson et al. [24]. The analysis results demonstrated that religious value orientation has a significant impact on all aspects of students' self-efficacy, except for social self-efficacy. In light of these findings, the study recommends that educators should motivate students to participate in school-based social groups. This participation can help students develop skills that enhance their social competence. Additionally, it is advised that teachers engage students in religious discussions and activities. Such engagement can foster a positive religious stance, guiding their actions and decisions. Second, Nikfarjam et al. [25] aimed to ascertain the connection between students' religious attitudes and their levels of self-control and self-discrepancy. They found a significant correlation, indicating a positive association between religious attitudes and self-control. Third, Anderson et al. [26] investigated how students' religious backgrounds influence off-campus programs. They found changes in religious identities, showing the influence of religion on student development. Then, a study by Prastiwi et al. [27] revealed that character values like integrity are integrated into activities such as Karawitan, indicating that religious education can positively influence students' integrity and other character values. Last, Nelson [28] explored how educators balance being a teacher with being a religious person, affecting their dispositions and potentially influencing student integrity. This study highlights the impact of teachers' religious beliefs on their professional conduct and, by extension, on their students.

Secondly, *cultural values influence student integrity*. Meanwhile, the research is in line with the results of this study. First, Ma [29] discussed how multicultural environments impact college students' ideological and political education. The study highlights how cultural values shape students' views of life, values, and the world, especially in multicultural contexts. Second, Sankofa [30] explored African American students' attitudes toward learning and achievement, showing how cultural integrity can influence educational success and student integrity. The results of their study indicate that students' favorable attitudes towards academic achievement are influenced by their value orientation regarding the necessary actions for success. Then, a study by Owusu-Agyeman [31] studied the significance of intercultural relationships between diverse university students. Recognizing and appreciating individual differences in the classroom fosters feelings of acceptance and social connectedness that

can impact student integrity. The fourth study focuses on the relationship between cultural values and student evaluation of teaching. It discovered that cultural values such as individualism versus collectivism and power distance significantly affect evaluation scores, suggesting that teaching performance may be valued differently depending on the composition of the student body [32].

Zhou [33] conducted research focused on the influence of communal cultural values on the propensity of Asian and Latinx college students to seek mental health assistance. The study revealed that a strong alignment with Interdependent Orientation values correlated with a reduced acknowledgment of the need for mental health care and more adverse perceptions of mental health services. This finding underscores the significant impact that cultural norms and values have on the attitudes and behaviors of students regarding mental health treatment. Last, Trudeau et al. [19] delved into the influence of campus traditions on student life within the campus environment, highlighting that cultural values affect integrity and character. Cultural values are implemented as student independence in completing school tasks, having a responsible attitude towards tasks and other activities, speaking politely with peers and teachers, and respecting elders. Within the community, various cultural values are interconnected within a system that serves as a guideline for ideal concepts in culture, strongly influencing the direction of community life.

Thirdly, *Gender influences the relationship between religious values and student integrity*. Gender, as an individual characteristic, influences behavior, attitudes, and actions. Females tend to use emotions more in actions, behavior, and attitudes, unlike males who are more inclined to use logic, thus appearing more unemotional. In the research findings, gender does not have an impact on the relationship between religious values and student integrity levels. Religious values are inherently taught from an early age, so their impact on integrity is not significantly large. In line with this, a study conducted by Estellas [34] evaluated the religious understanding and perspective of third-year college students, discovering that female students exhibited greater knowledge of their Catholic beliefs compared to their male counterparts. Nonetheless, this research did not specifically explore how gender influences the connection between religious values and student integrity. Then, the research did not identify any gender-based differences in the relationship between the quality of instruction and mental health issues among undergraduate students during the COVID-19 pandemic [35]. Another study conducted by Karimzadeh et al. [36] found that there was no significant difference between male and female students in the variables of religious attitude and academic achievement. The study entitled *How Do Students Become Good Workers?* By Chen [37] examines the relationship between career decision-making self-efficacy and career exploration, finding no moderating effect of gender. These studies collectively suggest that while religious values significantly influence student integrity, the impact of gender on this relationship is not substantial. In a different study, it was revealed that there were no discernible differences in resilience or life values based on gender or the location of student residence. The study found that students who exhibited higher levels of resilience also demonstrated stronger life values [38].

This research reveals that the academic integrity of male students is lower than that of female students. However, when looking at religious values, both male and female students have the same average. This implies that the application of religious values in the school environment follows school regulations similarly, but behavior and actions depend on opportunities and the environment among peers [36]. Therefore, the religious values applied in the school environment focus on what the school rules are, but student behavior and actions depend on the opportunities available, the situations faced, and the influence of peers in the school [39]. For example, in the context of education, religious values are defined as educational efforts connecting faith traditions and worship in daily life to enhance abilities, character formation, and individual achievements. In contrast, in community environments, the pursuit of deeper religious knowledge is still low, for instance, rarely participating in community religious studies [40]. Fundamentally, religious values will strengthen the morals and ethics of students.

Fourthly, *Gender influences the relationship between cultural values and student integrity*. Based on the analysis, it is observed that gender impacts the relationship between cultural values and student integrity. This means that both male and female students impact cultural values, thereby enhancing student integrity. In line with this, research conducted by Saadah et al. [41] investigates gender inequalities in academic and professional societies, focusing on annual conferences and meetings. The study highlights the exclusivity of these spaces for women, particularly affecting women of color and those from the Global South. Then, Chen et al. [37] investigated the link

between high school students' self-efficacy in making career decisions and their engagement in career exploration, focusing on the potential moderating roles of gender and school type. However, it was found that gender did not have a moderating effect on this relationship. Another study, Gimenez-Jimenez [42] delves into the effects of risk aversion and cultural factors on the advancement of student entrepreneurs in the venture creation process, paying special attention to differences based on gender. It suggests that female students' perceptions of risk-taking behaviors are linked to a slower progression in the venture development process, emphasizing the role of cultural context in shaping these outcomes.

In another case, a study conducted by Uyanne [43] found that the observed results, highlighting the significant differences in violence experienced by male and female students in schools, have direct implications for the development of student integrity, particularly in terms of gender. The increased incidence of physical and sexual harassment, as well as the marginalization faced by female students, underscores the need for educational strategies that not only address gender-based violence but also foster an environment conducive to the holistic development of integrity in all students, regardless of gender [5]. This awareness can guide educators, especially in Nigeria, to implement practices and policies that support the growth of integrity and ethical behavior, taking into account the unique challenges faced by female students.

In the scope of education addresses the influence of gender, in conjunction with other variables such as pathways to graduation and family cultural capital, on undergraduates' learning outcomes in general education courses. It revealed notable disparities in the learning outcomes reported by male and female students Xie et al. [44] and Mutambik et al. [45] examines the impact of gender and additional factors such as routes to graduation and familial cultural capital on the learning outcomes of undergraduates in general education courses. The findings indicated substantial differences in the learning outcomes as reported by male and female students. Trudeau [19] delved into the influence of campus traditions on student life within the campus environment, highlighting that cultural values affect integrity and character. In this regard, gender plays a role in the implementation of cultural values, impacting the level of student integrity.

Theoretically, female students are usually more aware of existing rules in schools and communities than male students. In the school environment, female students are mostly more likely to obey school rules because they tend to feel fear and shame when punished. In contrast, male students, if they see a beneficial opportunity, are not afraid of punishment [46]. Similarly, in the community environment, the focus on culture for women is more intense than for men. Women must maintain their dignity and reputation in the community to be seen as virtuous, whereas men are generally given more freedom as long as they adhere to existing cultural norms [47]. Cultural values are implemented in the form of student independence in completing school tasks, having a responsible attitude towards tasks and other activities, speaking politely with peers and teachers, and respecting elders. In the community, numerous cultural values are interconnected within a system, and this system serves as a guideline for ideal concepts in culture, strongly influencing the direction of community life [48].

Furthermore, to complete the findings, the researcher also provided an important role for educators in the teaching and learning process. Bukhari [49] explain the preaching of psychology perspective represents a sophisticated approach that synergizes fundamental religious principles with established psychological theories. This fusion aims to facilitate a deeper and more nuanced understanding of personal development and life quality enhancement. It serves as a theoretical framework for appreciating the influence of religiosity, particularly emphasizing the critical role of religious values in the cultivation of marital satisfaction. This approach underscores the interplay between spiritual beliefs and psychological well-being in a comprehensive and academic context. Then, in Islamic Psychology, an educator who embodies a peace character, marked by an unwavering belief in Allah's power and conscientious observance of religious laws, is not only deeply aware of Allah's constant presence in their life but also plays a crucial role in aiding students. This educator's strong spiritual and moral foundation is essential in guiding students, not just academically, but also in their personal and spiritual growth, fostering an environment where students can develop holistically under the vigilant and nurturing influence of such a spiritually [50; 51]. The findings may not be generalizable to all cultural and religious contexts, as this research may be limited to specific particular contexts.

CONCLUSION

Interestingly, from the data analysis, it was observed that only cultural values contribute significantly to the formation of student integrity, while religious values do not have a significant effect. Gender as a moderating variable also influences the relationship between cultural values and student integrity. Conversely, gender as a moderating variable does not have a significant impact on the relationship between religious values and student integrity. These values shape norms and moral expectations that influence students' attitudes and behaviors. A limitation in this study lies in the research method, where qualitative measurement tools such as open interviews must be used to obtain more complex results. Limitations in time and resources might have affected the depth of analysis and scope of the study.

This research only involved High School Students, hence generalizing these findings to student populations in other regions or with different cultural backgrounds may require further testing. Future researchers are advised to conduct similar studies in various cultural and religious contexts to validate and expand findings, such as in multicultural environments including schools, universities, and workplaces, which consist of diverse religions, genders, and backgrounds. Then, further research with more extended time and adequate resources could provide more comprehensive results.

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